

Has the EU Truly Become a Security Provider?

Institutional Progress and Political Limits in European Defence

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Working Paper

Version 1 | April 2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19558497

Abstract

This working paper examines whether the European Union (EU) can plausibly be understood as a security provider after Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine and the adoption of the Strategic Compass in 2022. It argues that the EU has made significant institutional advances in security and defence, including expanded coordination, capability initiatives, and financial support instruments. At the same time, persistent capability shortfalls, fragmented defence procurement, and enduring political divisions among the member states continue to constrain the Union's capacity for credible and sustained action. The paper therefore contends that the EU is best understood as a conditional security provider: an actor that has strengthened its role through the Strategic Compass, the Common Security and Defence Policy, and instruments such as the European Peace Facility, but remains limited by material weaknesses, intergovernmental politics, and continued reliance on the transatlantic security architecture. The EU's post-2022 trajectory thus reflects substantial progress in European defence, but not a complete transformation into a fully autonomous strategic actor.

Keywords

European Union; EU security and defence; Strategic Compass; strategic autonomy; Common Security and Defence Policy; CSDP; European Peace Facility; European defence policy; European defense policy; security provider

Introduction

Russia's full-scale invasion of Ukraine in 2022 forced the European Union (EU) to confront a question it had long avoided: can the EU actually provide security? The war fundamentally altered Europe's security environment and intensified debates about the Union's role in defence and crisis management. This invasion has been described as a "geopolitical awakening" for the European Union, prompting renewed debates about the Union's capacity to assume greater responsibility for its own security (Youngs 2022).

For decades, the EU had primarily been perceived as an economic and regulatory power, while military security remained largely the domain of NATO and the member states (Manners 2002, pp. 238–242; Duchêne 1972).

The adoption of the Strategic Compass in 2022 signalled an attempt to rethink this role. The document explicitly describes the ambition for the EU to become a stronger "security provider" capable of protecting European interests and contributing to international stability (Council of the European Union 2022a, p. 15). Subsequent institutional, financial and operational developments appear to support this ambition.

Among the most prominent initiatives is the creation of the Rapid Deployment Capacity (RDC) of up to 5,000 troops, intended to enable the EU to respond rapidly to crises (Council of the European Union 2022a, p. 25). At the same time, defence spending across Europe has increased significantly since 2022 (SIPRI 2023, p. 1). This upward trend continued in 2024, when total defence expenditure by the 27 EU member states reached €343 billion, marking a 19% increase from 2023 and bringing defence expenditure to 1.9% of GDP (European Defence Agency 2025, p. 3). Yet defence investment and procurement remain fragmented across EU member states (Clapp 2024, p. 3).

These developments raise a more precise analytical question: under what conditions can the EU be considered a security provider, and to what extent have post-2022 reforms altered those conditions?

This question reflects a broader scholarly debate about the EU's evolving role in international security. Traditionally, the EU has been conceptualised as a civilian or normative power that relies primarily on economic instruments, diplomacy and multilateral cooperation rather than military force (Manners 2002, pp. 238–242; Duchêne 1972).

However, the growing instability in Europe's neighbourhood, combined with shifting transatlantic relations and increasing geopolitical competition, has brought renewed attention to the question of whether the Union must develop stronger security and defence capabilities in order to remain an effective international actor (Helwig 2020, p. 4; Council of the European Union 2022a, p. 10).

This shift does not simply replace earlier conceptions of the EU as a civilian or normative power, but complicates them by raising the question of whether the Union can retain these characteristics while assuming a more active role in security and defence.

The EU has been discussed as a “security provider”, particularly in relation to the responsibilities it should assume beyond its borders (Biscop 2015, p. 11). The term therefore functions both as a policy aspiration and as an analytical category.

Here, a security provider can be understood as an actor that contributes to international and regional stability through the provision of security-related public goods, including crisis management, defence cooperation and financial or military support.

This does not require full strategic autonomy, but it does require that the EU possess the capacities necessary to organise, support and politically sustain security action in a credible manner over time.

To assess this question more systematically, this article draws on Helwig’s distinction between institutional, material and political autonomy (Helwig 2020, p. 8). Building on this framework, the analysis assesses the EU’s role as a security provider in terms of three dimensions: the institutional ability to organise collective security action, the material and operational means to support or deliver security, and the political cohesion required to deploy these instruments in a sustained and credible manner. This makes it possible to analyse the EU not in binary terms, but as a potentially conditional form of security provider.

The central question, therefore, is not simply whether the EU has expanded its defence instruments since 2022, but to what extent these reforms have strengthened the institutional, material and political conditions necessary for the Union to function as a credible security provider.

This article contributes to the debate by arguing that post-2022 developments cannot be captured adequately either by viewing the EU as an already consolidated security actor or by reducing it to its earlier civilian and regulatory roles. Rather, it positions itself between interpretations that emphasise the EU’s enduring civilian character, those that see it as an increasingly meaningful security actor, and those that stress the continued limits imposed by NATO dependence and intergovernmental fragmentation.

It argues that post-2022 reforms have strengthened important institutional and material conditions of EU security provision. However, the intergovernmental structure of defence decision-making and the continued fragmentation of military capabilities limit the extent to which the Union can function as an autonomous strategic actor (Helwig 2020, pp. 10–11). The EU is therefore best understood as a conditional security provider: one that contributes to security in meaningful ways, but within persistent political, institutional and transatlantic constraints.

The Strategic Shift: From Geopolitical Awakening to Operational Ambition

The Strategic Compass, adopted in 2022, represents a turning point in the EU’s security discourse. It acknowledges the deterioration of Europe’s security environment and calls for stronger defence cooperation, improved military capabilities and enhanced crisis-management instruments (Council of the European Union 2022a, pp. 13–14, 19). By framing the EU as a

stronger “security provider,” the document signals an ambition to broaden the Union’s traditional identity as primarily a civilian or regulatory power (Council of the European Union 2022a, p. 14–15). Rather than simply replacing earlier conceptions of the EU as a civilian or normative power, this shift suggests an attempt to supplement them with a more explicitly security-oriented role.

This rhetorical reorientation has been accompanied by several concrete operational initiatives. One of the most visible manifestations of this ambition is the Rapid Deployment Capacity (RDC). Designed as a modular force package capable of operating in non-permissive environments, the RDC seeks to address long-standing shortcomings in EU crisis-management capabilities (Council of the European Union 2022a, p. 11). Unlike the earlier EU Battlegroups, which reached full operational capability in 2007 but have never been deployed, the RDC is intended to address previous shortcomings through regular exercises and improved operational planning (European Union 2014, p. 2; Council of the European Union 2022a, p. 30).

This suggests that the post-2022 agenda is concerned not only with expanding capabilities on paper, but also with addressing the longstanding implementation gap in EU defence policy. Yet whether the RDC can overcome the shortcomings of the Battlegroups remains uncertain, since these were not only operational but also political in nature.

At the same time, the EU has increasingly demonstrated its role in security provision through concrete operational and financial instruments, most notably through the European Peace Facility, which has been used to fund military assistance to Ukraine since 2022 (Council of the European Union 2022b, p. 2). In this sense, recent developments complicate earlier portrayals of the EU as relying primarily on civilian, regulatory or diplomatic instruments.

The use of the EPF is particularly significant because it illustrates a form of EU security involvement that goes beyond coordination or economic support and is directly linked to the financing of military assistance. In this sense, the EPF demonstrates conditional security provision by enabling militarily relevant support at EU level while leaving both the political authorisation and the underlying military capabilities in the hands of the member states. It thus highlights the structural limits of EU security provision, which remains dependent on member-state agreement and indirect forms of support rather than autonomous force projection.

Nevertheless, it remains unclear whether the use of the EPF for military support to Ukraine marks a lasting structural shift in the EU’s security role or an exceptional response to a major war on the European continent. Moreover, the EU continues to conduct military and civilian missions under the Common Security and Defence Policy, such as Operation EUFOR Althea in Bosnia and Herzegovina, which remains an ongoing contribution to regional stability in the Western Balkans (European External Action Service 2026a; 2026b).

Alongside these operational developments, the EU has also increased its efforts to strengthen the European defence technological and industrial base. Initiatives promoting joint procurement, defence research and industrial cooperation aim to reduce strategic

dependencies and strengthen Europe's defence industrial capacity (Clapp 2024, pp. 1–4). These developments are closely linked to the broader debate on strategic autonomy.

In Helwig's account, strategic autonomy refers to the political, institutional and material capacity of the EU to pursue its own policy objectives while managing external dependencies (Helwig 2020, p. 8). At the same time, the term remains politically contested and is used differently across academic and policy debates (Council of the European Union 2021, p. 2). For that reason, Helwig's tripartite distinction is employed here not as a definitive definition, but as an analytical framework for assessing whether the EU possesses the capacities associated with credible security provision.

The period 2022 therefore represents a phase of accelerated institutional adaptation in EU security policy, as the Union has sought to translate geopolitical shock into structural reform. These developments suggest that the EU is increasingly seeking to operationalise what remains, at least in part, a policy ambition to act as a security provider, turning strategic intent into more concrete instruments and capabilities.

Institutional and Material Autonomy: Between Structural Innovation and Persistent Gaps

As noted above, Helwig proposes distinguishing between three dimensions: institutional autonomy, material autonomy and political autonomy (Helwig 2020, p. 8). The extent to which the EU can fulfil this role depends in particular on its level of institutional and material autonomy. The first two dimensions provide an important framework for assessing recent developments in EU defence policy.

Institutional autonomy refers to the existence of collective decision-making structures and planning capacities that allow the EU to coordinate security and defence actions (Helwig 2020, p. 8). Over the past decade, the Union has significantly expanded its institutional architecture in this field.

Several initiatives have contributed to this development, including Permanent Structured Cooperation (PESCO), the Coordinated Annual Review on Defence (CARD), the European Defence Fund (EDF) and the Military Planning and Conduct Capability (MPCC) (Molnár 2022, pp. 19–20). These mechanisms represent an effort to move beyond purely ad hoc cooperation toward more structured forms of defence integration. As Molnár notes, deeper defence cooperation since the mid-2010s has been organised around several institutional pillars, including the creation of PESCO, CARD, the MPCC, the European Peace Facility (EPF) and the European Defence Fund.

Collectively, these initiatives reflect the gradual institutionalisation of defence cooperation within the EU, as the Union has moved beyond predominantly ad hoc coordination towards more permanent structures for defence planning, joint capability development and policy coordination. Although these frameworks do not replace national armed forces or defence policies, they strengthen the EU's capacity to organise collective action at the European level and may contribute to more coherent defence planning and greater capability integration.

However, the significance of these developments should not be overstated, since stronger institutional coordination does not automatically translate into effective collective action in practice.

Material autonomy refers to the technological, industrial and military capabilities required to implement collective decisions (Helwig 2020, p. 8). Without sufficient capabilities and resources, institutional cooperation remains limited in its practical effect. In the context of EU defence policy, this dimension therefore encompasses both the development of military capabilities and the strength of Europe's defence technological and industrial base.

The European Defence Fund provides financial incentives for joint defence research and development projects, encouraging greater cooperation among member states and helping to reduce fragmentation in the European defence market (Clapp 2024, pp. 1; 4–5). By supporting collaborative projects across member states, the fund seeks to strengthen Europe's capacity to develop critical defence technologies and improve coordination in the European defence market. This is particularly important for defence market consolidation and the longer-term development of military capabilities, as greater coordination in research and procurement may reduce duplication and improve the efficiency of European defence investment.

These developments can therefore be interpreted either as evidence of gradual structural transformation or as partial, crisis-driven attempts to address long-standing capability deficits.

Nevertheless, important limitations remain. European defence procurement continues to be fragmented, with most procurement and defence planning still taking place at the national level, while many member states rely heavily on suppliers from outside Europe, particularly the United States (Clapp 2024, p. 3).

From the perspective of material autonomy, these limitations remain particularly significant. Strategic autonomy requires not only institutional mechanisms but also the technological, industrial and military capabilities necessary to implement collective decisions. As long as European defence procurement remains fragmented and heavily dependent on external suppliers, the Union's ability to act independently in security and defence policy will remain constrained.

Political Autonomy and the Limits of Strategic Cohesion

While institutional and material developments since 2022 indicate tangible progress, the most decisive dimension of strategic autonomy remains political.

Political autonomy refers to the ability of member states to align threat perceptions, strategic priorities and risk tolerance over time (Helwig 2020, p. 8).

Even when institutional mechanisms and material capabilities are strengthened, the effectiveness of EU security policy ultimately depends on political cohesion among member states. In EU security and defence policy, political autonomy is therefore particularly significant, since collective action depends not only on institutional structures or material capabilities but also on the willingness of national governments to act jointly in response to

external threats. Political autonomy is particularly decisive because institutional and material capacities can facilitate collective action, but they cannot substitute for the political consensus required to activate them.

The unanimity requirement in the Common Foreign and Security Policy means that collective action ultimately depends on political consensus among twenty-seven sovereign governments. As a result, even when institutional mechanisms and operational instruments exist, their activation requires agreement among member states with often differing strategic priorities and security perceptions. These differences are closely linked to the EU's geographical diversity and the varying security environments faced by its member states.

Although the Strategic Compass provides a shared threat assessment of the EU's strategic environment (Council of the European Union 2022a, p. 15), member states frequently approach security challenges from different geographical and political perspectives (European Parliament 2025, p. 6). For example, many Central and Eastern European countries prioritise territorial defence and deterrence in response to Russia, whereas other member states place greater emphasis on instability in the Southern neighbourhood, migration-related challenges, or broader security concerns in their neighbourhood.

Historical crises illustrate these divisions. The 2003 Iraq War and the 2011 Libya intervention are prominent examples in which EU member states failed to develop a common position (Helwig 2020, p. 11).

At the same time, the EU's security role remains closely embedded within the transatlantic security architecture, in which NATO and the EU play complementary and mutually reinforcing roles (NATO 2022, p. 10). NATO remains the central framework for collective defence in the Euro-Atlantic area (NATO 2022, p. 3).

Consequently, European defence initiatives are generally framed as complementary to NATO and as contributions to burden-sharing within the Alliance (NATO 2022, p. 10). Dependence on NATO does not necessarily preclude the EU from acting as a security provider, but it does limit stronger interpretations of the term that imply autonomous strategic action. This institutional relationship further illustrates the complex nature of the EU's emerging role as a security actor. While the Union increasingly contributes to crisis management, capability development and defence coordination, it does so within a broader security architecture that continues to rely heavily on NATO for collective defence.

As a result, the EU's security role often develops in parallel with – rather than independently from – transatlantic structures, reinforcing the idea that European defence integration remains embedded within a wider multilevel system of security governance.

Political cohesion thus emerges as the decisive variable shaping the effectiveness of EU security policy. While the Rapid Deployment Capacity may exist and institutional instruments continue to expand, their activation ultimately depends on the political will of member states. The EU can coordinate and facilitate collective action, yet it cannot compel it. The central issue, therefore, is not whether the EU possesses security-relevant instruments, but whether

political fragmentation prevents these instruments from amounting to a more autonomous form of security provision.

Conclusion: A Conditional Security Provider

The European Union has clearly moved beyond purely rhetorical ambitions in the field of security and defence.

Since the adoption of the Strategic Compass in 2022, the EU has expanded its institutional structures, increased defence coordination and introduced new initiatives aimed at strengthening its military capabilities (European External Action Service 2024). These developments demonstrate that the Union is gradually assuming a more active role in European security. Initiatives such as the Rapid Deployment Capacity, the European Defence Fund and Permanent Structured Cooperation indicate a growing willingness among member states to deepen defence cooperation.

However, these developments do not amount to full strategic autonomy. The EU can therefore no longer be understood solely through earlier conceptions of civilian or normative power, but neither can it be regarded as an unconstrained security actor. The intergovernmental nature of defence decision-making, persistent capability fragmentation and continued reliance on NATO all limit the Union's ability to act independently.

This conclusion reflects the broader pattern identified throughout the article: while institutional innovations and gradual improvements in military capabilities have strengthened the EU's role in security and defence, the Union's capacity to act ultimately remains dependent on the political cohesion of its member states.

The EU can therefore best be understood as a conditional security provider: an actor that increasingly contributes to European and international security but still operates within a multilevel system shaped by national sovereignty and transatlantic cooperation.

References

Biscop, Sven. 2015. *A New Strategy for EU Foreign and Security Policy*. IAI Working Paper 15/27. <https://www.egmontinstitute.be/app/uploads/2015/09/iaiw1527-def.pdf>

Clapp, Sebastian. 2024. *European Defence Industrial Strategy*. EPRS Briefing PE 762.402. Brussels: European Parliamentary Research Service. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/762402/EPRS_BRI\(2024\)762402_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2024/762402/EPRS_BRI(2024)762402_EN.pdf)

Council of the European Union. 2021. *Strategic Autonomy, Strategic Choices: Issues Paper*. Brussels: Council of the European Union. <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/49404/strategic-autonomy-issues-paper-5-february-2021-web.pdf>

Council of the European Union. 2022a. *A Strategic Compass for Security and Defence*. Brussels.

https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/strategic_compass_en3_web.pdf

Council of the European Union. 2022b. *Council Decision (CFSP) 2022/338 of 28 February 2022 on an Assistance Measure under the European Peace Facility for the Supply to the Ukrainian Armed Forces of Military Equipment*. *Official Journal of the European Union* L 60: 1–4. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32022D0338>

Duchêne, François. 1972. “Europe’s Role in World Peace.” In *Europe Tomorrow: Sixteen Europeans Look Ahead*, edited by Richard Mayne, 32–47. London: Fontana.

European Defence Agency. 2025. *Defence Data 2024–2025*. Brussels: European Defence Agency. https://eda.europa.eu/docs/default-source/brochures/2025-eda_defencedata_web.pdf

European External Action Service. 2024. *Progress on the Implementation of the Strategic Compass for Security and Defence*.

<https://www.eeas.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/2024/Implementation-of-strategic-compass-2024.pdf>

European External Action Service. 2026a. *Missions and Operations*. European External Action Service. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/missions-and-operations_en

European External Action Service. 2026b. *EUFOR Bosnia and Herzegovina Military Operation ALTHEA*. European External Action Service. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eufor-althea/eufor-bosnia-herzegovina-military-operation-althea_und_en?s=324

European Parliament. 2025. *Tackling Barriers to the Single Market for Defence*. Brussels: European Parliament.

https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2025/775283/EXPO_STU%282025%29775283_EN.pdf

European Union. 2014. *EU Battlegroups – Ready to Go?* Brussels: Publications Office of the European Union. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/d1ebe9f6-d952-43c2-af64-c12d7e0c1027/language-en>

Helwig, Niklas. 2020. *EU Strategic Autonomy: A Reality Check for Europe’s Global Agenda*. FIIA Working Paper 119. Helsinki: Finnish Institute of International Affairs.

https://www.fii.fi/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/wp119_strategic_autonomy-2.pdf

Manners, Ian. 2002. “Normative Power Europe: A Contradiction in Terms?” *Journal of Common Market Studies* 40 (2): 235–58.

<https://www.princeton.edu/~amoravcs/library/mannersnormativepower.pdf>

Molnár, Anna. 2022. “The Idea of a European Security and Defence Union.” In *Challenges of the Common Security and Defence Policy*, edited by Anna Molnár et al., 19–36. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Neli-Kirilova/publication/362189364_Elements_of_power_in_the_EU_Global_Strategy_for_Forei

[gn_and_Security_Policy/links/62daf2ac82bb47299298c507/Elements-of-power-in-the-EU-Global-Strategy-for-Foreign-and-Security-Policy.pdf](https://www.act.nato.int/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/290622-strategic-concept.pdf)

North Atlantic Treaty Organization. 2022. *NATO 2022 Strategic Concept*. Madrid. <https://www.act.nato.int/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/290622-strategic-concept.pdf>.

Stockholm International Peace Research Institute. 2023. *Trends in World Military Expenditure, 2022*. Stockholm: SIPRI. https://www.sipri.org/sites/default/files/2023-04/2304_fs_milex_2022.pdf

Youngs, Richard. 2022. “The Awakening of Geopolitical Europe?” *Carnegie Europe*, July 28. <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2022/07/the-awakening-of-geopolitical-europe>